

Table 1. POE and peroxidase activity in chloroplasts (X) and cytoplasm (Y) in rice leaves, 42 d after transplanting, Ludhiana, India.^a

Mn applied (mg/kg)	POE		Peroxidase	
	A	B	X	Y
0	9	18	0.60	4.8
2.5	14	28	0.48	4.8
5.0	14	28	0.40	5.4
10.0	15	29	0.38	6.4
15.0	16	30	0.39	4.7
20.0	17	32	0.35	4.2

^aA = OD at 620 nm/unit chlorophyll per 5 min; B = OD at 620 nm/100 mg fresh wt per 5 min; X = OD at 660 nm/60 s per unit enzyme in chloroplast; Y = OD at 660 nm/60 s per 100 mg fresh wt in cytoplasm.

in a pot experiment. Four seedlings were transplanted per pot and Mn was applied at 0, 2.5, 5.0, 10.0, 15.0, and 20.0 mg/kg of soil. Chloroplasts were isolated from leaves 21 and 42 d after transplanting and colorimetrically assayed for photosynthetic oxygen evolution (POE). Peroxidase activity in chloroplasts and cytoplasm was determined colorimetrically using guaiacol as substrate. Results at two growth stages were similar. Data for the 42d stage are given here.

Table 2. Elemental composition in rice leaves, yield, and DTPA Mn in soil, Ludhiana, India.

Mn applied (mg/kg)	Composition (mg/kg)				Yield (g/pot)		DTPA Mn in soil (mg/kg)
	Mn	Fe	Fe ²⁺	Zn	Grain	Straw	
0	53	510	174	30	2.4	40	7.7
2.5	71	485	95	32	4.4	42	10.5
5.0	70	402	100	36	5.9	38	11.8
10.0	115	305	104	34	7.2	39	13.4
15.0	81	278	86	36	7.6	39	15.3
20.0	93	265	83	30	8.4	41	19.3

POE was very low in Mn-deficient plants but increased with application of 2.5 mg Mn/kg. Applying more Mn did not proportionately increase POE (Table 1). Chloroplast peroxidase was highest in plants that received no Mn. Cytoplasmic peroxidase increased up to 10 mg Mn/kg and decreased slightly at higher rates.

Elemental analysis of leaves showed Mn concentration increased with Mn supply (Table 2). Fe²⁺ and total Fe content in leaves was highest in 0 Mn plants, indicating an inverse relationship with Mn concentration. Zn concentration did not change with Mn

application.

Grain yield was significantly higher (about 4 times more with 20 mg Mn/kg than with 0 Mn) with Mn application, but straw yield was about the same. Grain filling was incomplete in Mn-deficient plants. DTPA Mn content 42 d after transplanting had increased manyfold in all pots due to reduction under submerged conditions.

Results indicate that although rice plants did not show symptoms of Mn deficiency, low Mn decreased photosynthetic activity and impaired translocation of photosynthates to grain. *ℓ*

The Na-K ratio as index of salt stress in rice cultures

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We screened 16 rices for salt tolerance in coastal soils in South Gujarat.

Grain yield, and K and Na content, and their ratios in different rices, Navsari, India.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)	K (%)	Na (%)	Na:K
IET7587	2.6	0.51	1.05	2.06
IET7589	2.9	0.45	1.16	2.58
IET7908	1.8	0.36	1.05	2.92
IET7910	2.5	0.36	0.91	2.53
IET7911	2.3	0.32	0.91	2.84
IET6993	2.1	0.39	1.10	2.82
IET6996	2.6	0.40	1.17	2.92
IET7337	2.8	0.38	1.06	2.79
IET7588	3.4	0.52	0.99	1.90
IET7912	2.1	0.38	0.87	2.29
IR2031-729-2	3.5	0.57	0.68	1.19
SLR51214	2.8	0.40	1.04	2.60
CD at 5%	1.1	0.10	0.20	

SLR51214 was the check variety. At transplanting, soil had ECe 9.0 dS/m, pH 8.6, and ESP 25.

Twelve entries performed uniformly and at par with SLR51214. Grains were analyzed for nutrient content and Na:K was calculated (see table). K content varied from 0.32 to 0.57. IR2031-729-2 had highest K and lowest Na and yielded highest. Na:K for most varieties

was above 2.5. However, IR2031-729-2 had 1.19 and IET7588 had 1.90, indicating a preferential absorption of K over Na.

Yield and K content were highly and positively correlated ($r = 0.96$). The relation between yield and Na content was not significant. Na:K, however, was significantly and negatively correlated with yield ($r = -0.82$). *ℓ*

Azolla as a substitute for N fertilizer in rice cultivation

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In 1980-81 in Bhubaneswar, we studied azolla as a substitute for N fertilizer in rice cultivation. Soil was a laterite with pH 5.6, CEC 3.5 meq/100 g soil, 0.36% C, 0.35% N, 0.45% P, 1.55% K, 70.1%

sand, 16.3% silt, and 12% clay. The experiment was in a randomized block design with three replications. All plots received 10 cartloads of farmyard manure, 13.3 kg P, and 24.9 kg K/ha before transplanting Pusa 2-21 (IR8/TKM6). Azolla was surface applied or multiplied in situ 1 wk before transplanting. Plots received azolla alone or azolla with urea fertilizer (see table).

All treatments yielded more than the control. Applying 10 t azolla/ha